

Detection of Erratic Data using Fuzzy AutoEncoder

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ABSTRACT

Anomaly detection has been utilized in various data mining applications to identify unusual activity in the data. Anomaly detection is in great demand these days, due to advancements in the field of deep learning which produces more accurate findings. Anomaly detection is also increasingly being used extensively in industrial applications. This paper experimented with a deep learning technique Fuzzy AutoEncoder (FAE) for bearing vibration responses. Ball bearings play an important role in rotating machines. Bearings are the critical components for any system independent of the size of the machine. This component is critical, and any failure in them could cause the systems to shut down entirely. In such sensitive systems, a requirement for dependable Condition Monitoring (CM) on bearings with Outlier Detection (OD) is vital for keeping track of the system's health. CM with OD (CMOD) uses FAE to detect the abnormal data instances generated in sensors and provides only accurate data for fault prediction analysis. In this paper, the features are learned from encoded vibration signals and fixed thresholds based on the fuzzy membership function considered in the proposed FAE. Experimentation carried out with the proposed FAE achieved an average F1-score of 97.6% indicating that it provides more promising results than state-of-art techniques. This ensures data accuracy by detecting abnormality in bearing behavior before any analysis.

Keywords—AutoEncoder, Condition Monitoring, Deep learning, Fuzzy membership function, Outlier Detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

Outlier detection is the detection of abnormal data observations that raise suspicions by conflicting from normal instances. It may also be defined as the discovery of patterns in data that exhibit unexpected behavior. The raw data from sensors is highly vulnerable to noise which must be rectified and removed. The detection of outlier helps in better prediction of data. In conditional monitoring systems, OD can be used for irregular data detection.

Machine systems are becoming increasingly complicated and fulfilling vital duties in today's industry. The system's state should be checked to improve its reliability. Condition Monitoring (CM) is one way to increase machine dependability and lowering maintenance costs. The goal is to find abnormalities, flaws, and failures that aren't expected [1]. The major essentials of AD and CM system are the capacity to acquire relevant information and the usage of these features to assess the machine's worsening state by watching departures from normal (healthy) behaviour. Domain expertise and "trial and error" methodologies are required for manual feature engineering methods. Deep learning and current advancements in autoencoder-based techniques, on the other hand, have provided an alternate method for attribute extraction and dimensionality drop. By assessing the framework for CMOD based on FAE on a real-world dataset, its usefulness in both anomalous data detection and condition monitoring is demonstrated.

Fig. 1 Framework of proposed model

The proposed method's flowchart is shown in Fig. 1. After preprocessing the vibration signals in CMOD, the model will be trained to extract features. During testing, the FAE rebuilds the signal and classifies the abnormal instances through reconstruction error. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the information of related work carried-out for OD using machine learning and deep learning techniques. Section 3 discusses the recommended FAE technique for consistent feature extraction and outlier identification. Section 4 discusses the experimental results, whereas Section 5 discusses the conclusions and future study.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Deep learning has recently emerged as the go-to method for intelligent diagnostics of rotating machinery, and it has yielded a number of triumphs. It allows for building more agile model, and precise accuracy at the tradeoff of a reduced amount of severe regularization. To present a benchmark study, the author in [2] used seven datasets to evaluate four models: multi-layer perception (MLP), auto-encoder (AE), convolutional neural network (CNN), and recurrent neural network (RNN). Convolutional Neural Network are used to automatically categorize rotating tools imperfection and indication when protection activities to be conducted are proposed in paper work [3]. Author in [4] provides a new technique, which is an upgraded convolutional neural network-support vector machine (CNN-SVM). They do, however, have some flaws. To begin, feature engineering to effectively diagnose defects requires extraction and

selection of representative features from the original signal, which is a time-consuming and challenging task. The second problem is the disparity in social classes. Artificial neural networks and Time-frequency domain uniqueness, [5] attempted to identify distinct bearing classes. Paper [6] applied 1-D convolutional neural networks (CNN) to raw motor data to replace the human feature extraction stage. The comparison of their methodology to traditional feature extraction approaches on bearing fault detection revealed its superiority. Author in [7] employed an autoencoder to extract features, which were then used to develop a model for supervised defect detection and classification. In paper [8] investigation on different one-class classifiers was carried-out for detection of damaged rotor bars in an induction motor, including nearest neighbors and k-means. Deep neural network-based architectures, namely autoencoders, have been effectively used for supervised fault categorization into multiple fault categories utilizing time or frequency domain information retrieved from previous knowledge [9].

From above discussions, the existing RM outlier detection approaches experience from one or more of the following drawbacks:

- Time-consuming feature extraction equivalent to manual process [2,4,8],
- For model training and testing, extensive volumes of machine state labeled data are required, which is typically not accessible in the industry and complex to deal [2-6].
- Determines an appropriate threshold based on empirical equations to classify abnormal instances from original data was not flexible enough [2, 9].

In this paper, a FAE is trained to automatically keep track of RMs' status and extract time-domain features as an alternative to human feature extraction to overcome the aforementioned issues.

III. FUZZY AUTOENCODER IN CONDITION MONITORING OUTLIER DETECTION

The proposed FAE models takes original time-series vibration signals as input, learns the optimal features and determine the system's health based on these features, which performs outlier classification using fuzzy membership function.

A. Model Setup

Initially the parameter adjustment has to be carried out in the model setup. First, the thresholds τ_j must be set, which necessitates parameter modification. Experiments were conducted to optimize various values. Thresholds were calculated using a weighting coefficient. Thus, the threshold τ_j for each class $j = 1, \dots, N$ of each AE's error was set as the baseline AE's threshold τ_0 considered by the weight $w_j = 1-p_j$, where p_j is the fraction of instances of Class j [10].

During the training phase, every subset containing just one kind of event, such as Normal or Abnormal, is taught a specialized AE model. During the test phase, the root mean square error (RMSE) between the input is calculated.

Here, the equation (1) shows objective function that the model aims to minimize reconstruction error:

$$L_{(x_i, \hat{x}_i)} = \sum_i \|x_i - \hat{x}_i\|^2 \quad (1)$$

The equation (2) calculates the probability of the instances (training data) x for certain μ and σ^2 :

$$p(x|\tau) = p(x|\mu, \sigma) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{(x_i-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \tag{2}$$

The output error $r_{i,j}$ of each AE ($1 \leq i \leq X$ and $1 \leq j \leq C$, for X samples and C classes) is used to generate a fuzzy membership function for each input signal x_i , which offers an indication of the signal's proximity to the event class on which the AE model was trained. In our scenario, $C = 2$ interval membership functions are produced for each input sample, corresponding to the Normal and Abnormal categories. The interval-valued fuzzy membership function interval is formed by the values of both components.

Finally, interval comparison is utilized to estimate the degree of preference of each membership function, and then to determine the suitable event category, using a probabilistic method [10]. The suggested reconstruction-error-based membership function is illustrated in Fig. 2. Positive membership is represented by a continuous line (μ_U). Pessimistic membership is shown by a dashed line (μ_L).

Fig. 2 Proposed fuzzy reconstruction-error-based membership function

The two membership components are:

- a) Minor membership $\mu_{L,j}$, which is smallest when the sample is an outlier with respect to class j , i.e. $r_{i,j} > \tau_j$, and
- b) Major membership $\mu_{U,j}$, which is high when the sample is classified in class j , i.e. $r_{i,j} < \tau_j$ shown in equation (3)

$$\mu_{L,j}(\epsilon_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{\epsilon_{i,j}}{\tau_j} & \text{if } \epsilon_{i,j} \leq \tau_j \\ 0 & \text{if } \epsilon_{i,j} > \tau_j \end{cases}, \mu_{U,j}(\epsilon_{i,j}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \epsilon_{i,j} \leq \tau_j \\ 2 - \frac{\epsilon_{i,j}}{\tau_j} & \text{if } \tau_j < \epsilon_{i,j} \leq 2\tau_j \\ 0 & \text{if } \epsilon_{i,j} > 2\tau_j \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

The next section presents the results of proposed FAE discussing the experimental setup, dataset characteristics and evaluation of results.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Implementation setup

Ball bearings run in different speed and load condition. Mostly bearing life is based on fatigue condition [11]. Due to continuous running and different environment condition, there may be a possibility of defect creation and penetration in midway of running. Any defect in

bearing produces vibrations which is transmitted to other elements. So, monitoring process can be done by harvesting vibration signals. Because among different methods of condition monitoring, monitoring using vibration signals is mostly used for many machines since it is cheap and effective when compared to other method of diagnosis. Apart from bearing defect, the defect which is not associated with bearing also influences a vibration signature over the bearing. So, proper vibration analysis with suitable number of trials of experiments with different configurations is done. In general, collecting huge amounts of data is significantly easier than precisely obtaining their matching labels for rotating machine (RM) outlier detection. Data ambiguity makes it difficult to assign labels correctly, especially at a critical moment when machines exhibit early indicators of failure that are difficult to distinguish from fully established defects. The goal is for the system to be able to discover abnormalities that were previously unnoticed by replicating the machine's normal behaviour. The schematic drawing of the 6204 bearing is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Schematic sketch of 6204 bearing

Author in [12] proposed a design procedure and designed an experimental setup for carrying out vibrational analysis. By referring [12], design of experimental setup has been developed as suitable for generating dataset. The following table 1 and 2 shows details of the components which are readily available for deployment.

TABLE I. MOTOR SPECIFICATIONS

<i>Motor Specifications</i>	
Power	1 HP
Volts	220 V
Speed	1500 rpm
Current	4.6 A

TABLE II. SHAFT SPECIFICATIONS

<i>Shaft specifications</i>	
Material used	Stainless steel
Density of the shaft	8000 kg/m ³
Length of the shaft	1000mm
Diameter of the shaft	20mm

Mass of the shaft, $m = 2.51$ kg,

Weight of the shaft, $W = m.g = 24.6552 \text{ N}$,

Load per unit length, $w = \frac{W}{L} =$

$$\frac{24.6552}{1000} = 0.0246552 \text{ N/mm},$$

Yield Stress of shaft, $\sigma_{yield} = 215 \text{ MPa}$ (for stainless steel),

$$\text{Maximum shear stress, } \tau_s = \frac{0.5 \times \sigma_{yield}}{FOS} = \frac{0.5 \times 215}{3} = 35.833 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

The experimental setup and all the other accessories are fixed in order to rotate the shaft. The following fig. 4 shows the complete experimental setup used to rotate the shaft. The accelerometer is placed over the bearing and it also mentioned. Further the accelerometer is connected to the data acquisition system (DAQ).

Fig. 4 Completely connected experimental setup

Fig. 5 DAQ assisted with PC

The fig. 5 shows the DAQ used to read signals given by accelerometers and the DAQ is connected with the PC. The table 3 shows the trial readings of various features when the motor runs at 100 rpm speed. Those values in the excel sheets with values were considered for outlier detection.

TABLE III. MEASUREMENTS OF ACCELEROMETER TAKEN FOR DIFFERENT RPM SPEED

100	0.000171	0.055261	0.055261	0.003054	2.97158	-0.00118	-0.01211	0.136919	0.235913	0.446892
100	-0.00012	0.056105	0.056106	0.003148	2.963443	-0.00089	0.015443	0.131921	0.202687	0.38607
100	-0.00025	0.057418	0.057419	0.003297	3.070343	-0.00098	-0.00205	0.121075	0.215666	0.414702
100	0.000157	0.05525	0.055251	0.003053	3.141995	-0.00064	-0.00578	0.118907	0.227986	0.413736
100	0.000435	0.057651	0.057651	0.003324	3.215139	0.000272	0.009077	0.139807	0.304834	0.532897
100	-5.3E-05	0.055532	0.055533	0.003084	3.119582	-0.00143	-0.00855	0.125879	0.234178	0.462344
100	-0.00028	0.056207	0.056207	0.003159	3.037415	-0.00168	-0.00788	0.131144	0.226164	0.421702
100	-9.3E-05	0.056705	0.056706	0.003216	3.681634	-0.00031	0.00662	0.206489	0.385829	0.606734
100	0.000171	0.054496	0.054497	0.00297	3.055317	-0.00158	-0.01014	0.199801	0.220141	0.387022
100	-0.00017	0.059142	0.059143	0.003498	3.412831	-0.00043	0.002253	0.087413	0.256744	0.494157
100	0.000005	0.057974	0.057975	0.003361	3.12924	-0.00133	0.002275	0.220508	0.239504	0.42744
100	0.000071	0.055469	0.05547	0.003077	3.235853	-0.00091	-0.00663	0.142925	0.229647	0.433529
100	-0.00018	0.055356	0.055357	0.003064	3.067945	-0.00136	-0.00038	0.161855	0.253628	0.441749
100	0.000093	0.056507	0.056508	0.003193	3.379454	-0.00071	-0.00676	0.193101	0.246749	0.456779
100	-3.8E-05	0.057246	0.057247	0.003277	3.203524	-0.00059	0.004393	0.125193	0.257692	0.456394
100	-0.00028	0.054387	0.054387	0.002958	3.195278	-0.00214	-0.00499	0.154599	0.237419	0.421575
100	0.00014	0.056063	0.056063	0.003143	3.137235	-0.00067	-0.00383	0.137938	0.239032	0.462602
100	-3.2E-05	0.055831	0.055832	0.003117	3.232464	-0.00042	0.008138	0.173925	0.223428	0.473164
100	-0.00027	0.055337	0.055337	0.003062	3.15861	-0.00051	-0.00902	0.104627	0.265416	0.469125
100	0.000124	0.056404	0.056405	0.003182	3.29123	-0.00052	-0.00789	0.094418	0.243141	0.478151
100	0.00004	0.056767	0.056768	0.003223	3.502505	-0.00142	-0.0062	0.20987	0.260119	0.471355
100	-0.00038	0.056737	0.056737	0.003219	3.22589	-0.00013	0.003115	0.12834	0.295906	0.500497
100	0.000277	0.057016	0.057016	0.003251	3.196281	-0.00045	-0.0117	0.111918	0.207709	0.417924
100	-4.7E-05	0.05569	0.055691	0.003102	3.09119	-0.00093	-0.00081	0.145346	0.259856	0.469668
100	-0.00027	0.056945	0.056945	0.003243	3.073904	-0.00178	-0.02033	0.174243	0.224874	0.441804
100	0.000319	0.056522	0.056522	0.003195	3.104083	-0.00042	-0.0156	0.05419	0.269787	0.487848
100	-8.1E-05	0.054278	0.054279	0.002946	3.132613	-0.00058	-0.00054	0.105414	0.202352	0.386457
100	-0.00017	0.056511	0.056512	0.003194	3.00079	-0.00137	-0.01267	0.159987	0.207317	0.389364

150	-0.00014	0.069225	0.069226	0.004792	3.269323	-0.00216	-0.01267	0.147718	0.291281	0.547661
200	-0.00011	0.083577	0.083578	0.006985	3.363499	-0.00357	-0.01326	0.27504	0.41288	0.716199
250	0.000003	0.09264	0.092641	0.008582	3.354746	-0.00342	-0.01184	0.232495	0.438408	0.756712
300	0.000021	0.105405	0.105407	0.011111	3.128856	-0.00236	-0.00057	0.044798	0.384544	0.865422
350	0.000056	0.111392	0.111394	0.012409	3.119269	-0.00081	-0.00568	-0.0226	0.407598	0.818379
400	0.000027	0.127545	0.127548	0.016268	3.140143	-0.00145	-0.0203	-0.01385	0.461071	0.934706
450	0.000162	0.157015	0.157018	0.024655	2.996326	0.003916	0.056047	-0.06671	0.594031	1.156956
500	-3.7E-05	0.182095	0.182099	0.03316	2.957732	0.001533	0.026266	0.003457	0.605587	1.273232

The time series data after preprocessing is analyzed for outlier detection by considering the samples for training and testing in the model. During training only normal data is considered for obtaining the reconstruction threshold. Once the threshold for classifying normal and abnormal instances is obtained, the model is tested with various weights using fuzzy membership function.

The performance metrics considered for model evaluation is calculated as follows:

$$Precision_j = \frac{c_j}{e_j}$$

$$Recall_j = \frac{c_j}{r_j}$$

$$F1_j = \frac{2 * Precision_j * Recall_j}{Precision_j + Recall_j}$$

Where,

r_j, e_j and $(j \in \{1, 2\})$ are the number detected events for normal/abnormal class, respectively.

The Area Under Curve (AUC) is a measure of a model's capability to forecast the future. They're derived from comparing the true positive rate and false positive rate at different thresholds. The higher AUC value indicates that the model is more efficient in classification. Fig. 6 shows the plot of AUC of the proposed model in comparison to existing models [Artificial Neural Network (ANN), AutoEncoder (AE)].

Fig. 6 AUC Score for proposed FAE

The detection accuracy of the model can be verified by varying the number of outlier instance percentile during testing. This process makes the model to accurately classify outliers with minimum errors (in our case minimum false positives). This is shown in figure 7 which infers the model's detection accuracy.

Fig. 7 Comparison of Actual Outliers vs Predicted Outliers by FAE

Table 4 shows the results of normal vs. abnormal event classification ($p_{norm} = 0.80$ and $p_{anom} = 0.20$ are the proportions of normal and abnormal samples in the training set).

TABLE IV. EVALUATION OF MODELS' PERFORMANCE FOR OUTLIER CLASSIFICATION

Method	Weight (Normal instance)	Weight (Outlier instance)	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	AUC
ANN [2]	0.7	0.3	0.90	0.92	0.77	0.91	0.82
	0.8	0.2	0.89	0.92	0.80	0.87	0.81
	0.9	0.1	0.81	0.90	0.82	0.75	0.77
AE [7]	0.7	0.3	0.95	0.97	0.82	0.95	0.88
	0.8	0.2	0.93	0.95	0.85	0.91	0.85
	0.9	0.1	0.87	0.96	0.81	0.92	0.81
FAE	0.7	0.3	0.97	0.98	0.89	0.96	0.92
	0.8	0.2	0.95	0.97	0.86	0.91	0.90
	0.9	0.1	0.94	0.95	0.81	0.90	0.90

The findings in Table 4 demonstrate how effective it is to use a fuzzy membership function to improve outlier detection. The following are the key benefits and achieved gaps discussed section 2 by using the proposed FAE:

- The computation time of proposed FAE for feature extraction is minimal during training.
- The proposed model incurred good results for unlabeled data by using suitable parameters in the AE.
- Fuzzy membership function implemented with AE resulted in fixing suitable threshold than standard techniques.
- In terms of overall accuracy and correct categorization of normal/ outlier occurrences, the suggested approaches outperform the state-of-the-art ANN and AE. Despite their disproportional distribution, the accuracy, recall, and the F1 score obtained are more evenly distributed for classification.
- For the Anomalous class, the effect of utilizing imbalanced weights is more pronounced, with greater accuracy when w_j is higher.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Deep learning approaches, when applied to anomaly detection, provide several benefits. These approaches, for starters, are designed for multivariate and high-dimensional data. This simplifies the process of combining data from many sources and avoids the difficulties of separately modelling anomalies for each variable and aggregating the findings. The proposed FAE is modeled with complicated, nonlinear connections within data, making it suitable for focusing on research gaps identified in section 2. From experimental outputs of bearing, the features are learned through proposed FAE model and trained in the manner to classify the normal instances from abnormal instances with the help of fuzzy membership functions. It is also observed that the proposed approach showed a high performance in detecting outliers, and it can be applied to more general applications. The experimental results infer that the proposed model produced 97% detection accuracy and improved the quality of data suitable for bearing fault analysis. Other options for determining a threshold value will be examined in future research. Advanced autoencoders, such as variational autoencoders, can also be used to train the model, since they strive to model the data distribution rather than learning to re-create the normal data points. This suggests that datasets containing both normal and abnormal cases can be used.

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